

DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION AND STABILITY INDICATING OF UV - SPECTROSCOPY METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ASCORBIC ACID AND PIPERINE

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ABSTRACT

Antioxidants like vitamins, polyphenols, and flavonoids protect the body by neutralizing harmful free radicals from various sources. Ascorbic acid (ASA) and piperine (PP) are well-studied antioxidants, playing key roles in several diseases. Owing to their exciting synergistic potential and combination delivery applications, we developed a simple and rapid UV spectroscopy method based on isosbestic point detection. A linear relationship was identified between absorbance readings and corresponding concentrations ranging from 0-30 µg/ml, with correlation coefficients (R^2) of 0.995 for ASA and 0.998 for PP respectively. The detection limits were determined at 4.56µg/ml and 2.89µg/ml, while the quantitation limits were set at 14.12µg/ml and 8.77µg/ml for ascorbic acid and piperine, respectively. The recovery percentages of 50%, 100 % and 150% varied from 49.3% to 51%, 102.4% to 102.8% and 150% to 150.7% for both, accompanied by correspondingly low %RSD values, signifying the analytical method's high accuracy. The percent relative standard deviation of ASA and PP mixture, the intra-day analysis was determined and found

to be 1.034% at λ_1 and 1.121% at λ_2 , respectively. In the inter-day study, the % RSD was found to be 1.075% at λ_1 and 1.679% at λ_2 , respectively. From the findings, we conclude that our method is both precise and accurate. We further validated our method through forced degradation studies under acidic, alkaline, oxidative, photolytic, and thermal conditions, confirming the susceptibility of both compounds to degradation. These findings underscore the reliability of our simultaneous UV spectroscopic approach for stability analysis and future pharmaceutical research.

KEYWORDS: UV spectroscopy, Simultaneous estimation, Ascorbic acid, Piperine, Validation.

INTRODUCTION

In the pharmaceutical development of a new formulation, it is essential to identify and measure the medication to optimize formulation parameters such as stability. Antioxidants can decrease or inactivate free radicals and/or reduce oxidative damage (Hassan et al. 2024). Our formulation comprises a dual medication system consisting of Ascorbic Acid (ASA) and Piperine (PP). Our future objective is to augment immunomodulatory potential through the combination of ASA and PP, as both medicines possess the capacity to address immune-related disorders. Ascorbic acid (Fig. 1a), commonly referred to as vitamin C, is an organic acid with antioxidant capabilities that participate in several activities within living cells. In the human organism, ASA plays a complex and vital role by safeguarding active biological molecules from oxidative degradation, enhancing immune system functions, and stimulating the manufacture of collagen, steroid hormones, and certain neurotransmitters (Trifunski et al. 2022; Afkhami-Ardekani et al. 2007). It is a crucial nutrient that significantly contributes to safeguarding the organism against infections, inflammatory illnesses, and preserving biomembranes from peroxide damage (El-Borm et al. 2019).

Piperine (Fig. 1b) is an alkaloid extracted from the fruits of the black pepper plant (*Piper nigrum* Linn). Due to its unique pungency and flavor, black pepper is esteemed as the foremost spice in culinary applications, gaining the title "the king of spices". Traditional Indian, Chinese, and Arabic medicine has utilized black pepper for various ailments for an extensive period (AbouAitah et al., 2020). PP has several pharmacological effects, encompassing antioxidant, anti-arthritic, anti-inflammatory, and anti-depressant characteristics. Numerous studies on piperine have been performed alongside other phytochemicals, leading to improved bioavailability and both preventative and therapeutic

effects (Kurangi and Jalapure 2020). Piperine's medicinal properties render it a formidable choice for addressing various diseases.

Fig. 1: Chemical structure of (a) Ascorbic acid (b) Piperine.

Formulating a combination presents a problem for simultaneous examination and identification of both drugs utilized. Among the several methods for drug determination, spectrophotometry remains favored due to its simplicity, specificity, and cost-effectiveness (Jain *et al.* 2011). Following an comprehensive literature review, it was noted that only isolated methodologies for the examination of both medicines are accessible.

Isosbestic point enables easy, accurate quantification and interpretation by providing a common wavelength for compounds with different absorption maxima (Lotfy *et al.* 2014). Based on isobestic point, we have developed and validated for the concurrent estimation of ASA and PP using UV spectroscopy.

The developed method is straightforward, sensitive, precise, and reproducible, which can be validated by assessing the stability of ASA and PP under stressful conditions. Forced degradation testing of pharmaceutical compounds is mandated by International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines to ascertain the compound's intrinsic stability by delineating a degradation pathway and identifying probable degradation products (Tayde 2024). This will demonstrate that the methodology utilized for the analysis is robust and effective. "Stability testing of innovative pharmaceutical compounds and products, in accordance with ICH standards Q1A (R2) and Q1B, must be performed under diverse conditions, encompassing extreme temperatures, oxidation, photolysis, and hydrolysis across a wide pH spectrum (Singh *et al.* 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Instrumentns

Shimadzu UV-1600 series equipment was utilized in conjunction with a quartz cuvette featuring a 1 cm path length. Software utilized was UV Probe version 4.2. The investigation utilized a digital analytical balance (Wenstar DA14-222) and an ultrasonic sonicator (Equitron). Validated pipettes of 1, 2, and 5 ml; volumetric flasks of 10 and 100 ml; and beakers of 100, 250, and 500 ml were constructed from Borosil glass.

Chemicals and Reagents

Pure Drug samples of Ascorbic acid and Piperine were purchased from Yucca Enterprises, Mumbai, India. Methanol was purchased from Merck Limited, Mumbai. All chemicals and reagents were of AR Grade.

Selection of wavelength

10 mg of accurately weighed ASA was dissolved in methanol in a 100 ml standard volumetric flask, and volume was adjusted to 100 ml with methanol to attain a concentration of 100 μ g/ml. 1 ml of the aforementioned stock solution was pipetted and transferred into a 10 ml standard volumetric flask, with the volume adjusted to 10 ml using methanol to achieve a concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The above solution was subsequently analyzed between 200-400 nm against a blank sample.

Similarly, 10 mg of PP was precisely weighed and dissolved in methanol within a 100 ml standard volumetric flask, and the volume was adjusted to 100 ml using methanol to achieve a concentration of 100 μ g/ml. From 1 ml of the aforementioned stock solution was pipetted and put into a 10 ml standard volumetric flask, and the volume was adjusted to 10 ml with methanol to achieve a concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The aforementioned solution was analyzed within the 200-400 nm range against the reagent blank.

Concurrent development and validation of ascorbic acid and piperine in methanol via UV spectroscopy

The absorbance of two drug samples were measured at their respective maximum absorption wavelengths for the quantitative analysis of two components using the simultaneous equation method. The absorbances of ascorbic acid and piperine were measured at selected wavelengths of 275 nm (λ_1) and 267 nm (λ_2), respectively. The absorptivity coefficients for each drug were determined at both wavelengths. Absorbance and absorptivity coefficients

were correctly replaced into the equations, resulting in the determination of the concentration values of each medicine in the mixture. Concentrations of two medicines in a 1:1 mixture at 275 nm and 267 nm were determined utilizing the following equation:

$$C_x = \frac{R_M - R_Y}{R_X - R_Y} \times \frac{A_1}{ax_1}$$

$$C_Y = \frac{R_M - R_X}{R_Y - R_X} \times \frac{A_2}{ay_1}$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 are absorbance of combination at 275nm and 267 nm.

ax_1 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of ASA at 275nm (248)

ay_1 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of PP at 275 nm (281)

ax_2 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of ASA at 267 nm (149)

ay_2 = A (Absorptivity, 1 %, 1 cm) of PP at 267 nm (301);

C_x and C_y represent the unknown concentrations of ASA and PP, respectively, in the sample solution.

$$R_M = A_2/A_1, R_X = ax_2/ax_1 \text{ and } R_Y = ay_2/ay_1$$

A_1 and A_2 denote absorbance of the combination at 275 nm and 267 nm, respectively; ax_1 and ax_2 represent the absorptivities of ASA at λ_1 and λ_2 , whereas ay_1 and ay_2 indicate the absorptivities of PP at λ_1 and λ_2 , accordingly. C_x and C_y denote the concentrations of ASA and PP, respectively.

At 275 nm, solutions of both drugs at same amount had similar absorbance, resulting in no change. Wavelengths exhibiting similar absorptivity for the two species are referred to as isobestic or iso-absorptive points (Guideline, IHT 2005; Majithia et al. 2020).

Preparation of standard stock solution

Precisely measured quantities of 10 mg of ASA and 10 mg of PP were individually transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Initially, approximately 50 ml of methanol was added into flask and subjected to sonication. The volume was adjusted to the mark with methanol to make stock solutions of 100 μ g/ml of ASA and 100 μ g/ml of PP. Subsequently, requisite quantity of this stock solution was diluted with methanol to produce standard solutions varying from 5 to 30 μ g/ml for each drug. Absorbance of resultant solutions was quantified at peak absorption wavelengths of 275 and 267 nm, respectively.

Preparation of test solution for assay

Weighed approximately 10 mg of ASA and PP, dissolve them in methanol in a 100 ml standard volumetric flask, and adjust volume to 100 ml with methanol to attain a concentration of 100 μ g/ml. The solution was filtered using Whatman filter paper no. 41. From aforementioned stock solution, 1 ml was pipetted and transferred into a 10 ml standard volumetric flask, and volume was adjusted to 10 ml with methanol to achieve a concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The solution was scanned within the range of 200-400nm in comparison to the reagent blank.

Preparation of calibration curve

Aliquots of 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, and 3.0 ml were accurately transferred from working standard solutions of ASA and PP (100 μ g/ml) into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks using a validated 1 ml pipette. Each flask was then diluted to mark with methanol using a validated 10 ml pipette. The results produced concentrations of 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 30 μ g/ml of ASA. Absorbance of the resulting solutions was assessed at maximum absorption wavelengths of 275 and 267 nm, respectively.

Method Validation as per ICH guidelines Q2 (R1)

The proposed technique has been validated in accordance with ICH guidelines Q2 (R1) (Guideline, IHT 2005).

Linearity and Range

Study of linearity involved the preparation of standard solutions at six distinct amounts. The linearity range for ASA and PP was determined to be 0–30 μ g/ml, respectively. Absorbance of ASA and PP was measured at λ_1 and λ_2 for each solution. Calibration curves of absorbance against concentration were constructed. Linear relationship between absorbance responses and concentrations was established by linear regression analysis. Experiment was conducted in triplicate (Sultana *et al.* 2022).

Precision

Accuracy of suggested method was evaluated by repeatability, intra-day precision, and inter-day precision. Repeatability was assessed by doing six replicates of sample solution. Intermediate precision was assessed by evaluating the responses of six replicates on the same and different days for a test solution containing ASA and PP at a concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The results were expressed as a % RSD (Sultana *et al.* 2022).

Accuracy

Recovery investigations were conducted using the conventional addition approach. A specified quantity of standard ASA and PP (5, 10, and 15 µg/ml), corresponding to 50%, 100%, and 150% of the label claim, was included into a test solution of ASA and PP (10 µg/ml). The identical investigation was conducted thrice, at each stage of recovery (Sultana et al. 2022).

Detection and quantitation limits

Detection limit (DL) is the minimal concentration of the analyte that can be accurately identified, reflecting the precision of the instrumental response. Quantitation limit (QL) denotes the minimal amount of analyte in a sample that can be measured with adequate precision and accuracy. QL and DL were calculated using equations (1) and (2), which are based on the standard deviation and slope of the acquired response. Where σ is the standard deviation of the intercept of calibration plot and S represents the slope of the calibration curve (Ali et al. 2022).

Limit of Detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) of the new method were determined from calibration curve utilizing the equation,

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma/S \quad \dots \text{eq. (1)}$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma/S \quad \dots \text{eq. (2)}$$

Where, σ = standard deviation of y-intercepts of regression lines of calibration curves, S = the average of the slopes of calibration curves.

Forced degradation studies

Forced degradation experiments of ASA and PP were conducted to evaluate the efficacy of the analytical approach. To establish a stability-indicating test method, UV-spectrophotometry in methanol was employed. Stability indicating UV-spectrophotometric assay technique for the simultaneous assessment of ASA and PP was carried out first time (Ali et al. 2022).

Sample preparation for forced degradation

ASA and PP were subjected to degradation under various circumstances, including acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic environments. The subsequent degrading techniques employed were:

Stress degradation by hydrolysis under acidic condition

A 10ml volumetric flask was prepared with 1ml each of stock solutions (100 μ g/ml) of ASA and PP, followed by the addition of 1ml of 0.1M HCl, and the volume was adjusted to the mark with methanol. After 60 minutes, the solution was injected into the cuvette, and absorbance was measured at the specified λ_{\max} for both medications. Percentage recovery and percentage degradation of both medicines were assessed using the proposed simultaneous UV equation approach (Ali et al. 2022).

Stress degradation by hydrolysis under alkaline condition

A 10ml volumetric flask was prepared with 1ml each of stock solutions (100 μ g/ml) of ASA and PP, followed by the addition of 1ml of 0.1 M NaOH, and the volume was adjusted to the mark with methanol. Following a 60-minute period, the solution was injected into the cuvette, and absorbance was measured at the designated λ_{\max} for both drugs. Percentage recovery and percentage deterioration were ascertained utilizing simultaneous UV equation method that was established (Sultana et al. 2022).

Oxidative degradation

In a 10 ml volumetric flask, 1 ml each of ASA and PP stock solutions (100 μ g/ml) was combined with ml of 30% w/v hydrogen peroxide using methanol. The volumetric flask was maintained at room temperature for 15 minutes. 1 ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide was maintained at room temperature overnight in a 10ml volumetric flask. Both solutions were subjected to boiling in a water bath to eradicate any residual hydrogen peroxide. After 15 minutes, dilutions of the stock solution were performed to achieve the target concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The solution was subsequently positioned in a cuvette and underwent UV examination (Sultana et al. 2022).

Thermal degradation

ASA and PP samples were positioned on a Petri dish and subjected to heating at 80°C for duration of 24 hrs. After 24 hours, 1 mg of each sample was individually diluted with methanol to a final volume of 10 ml. The resulting concentration was 10 μ g/ml for each medication. The solutions were gathered in a cuvette for UV-vis analysis (Sultana et al. 2022).

Photolytic degradation

ASA and PP samples were exposed to direct sunlight for 4 hrs. 1 mg of each sample was placed in separate 10 ml volumetric flasks, dissolved in methanol, and the volume was adjusted to 10 ml to provide a concentration of 10 μ g/ml. The sample was subsequently positioned in a cuvette for UV analysis (Sultana *et al.* 2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the diverse findings of our testing, demonstrating an acceptable UV spectrophotometric method applicable at various stages of the study. Solutions of ASA and PP, each with a concentration of 10 μ g/ml, were successfully produced independently and scanned within the 200-400 nm range. The absorbance ratio method uses ratio of absorbance at two selected wavelengths, one of which is an iso-absorptive point and other being the λ_{max} of one of two components. The overlay spectra of the two drugs, it was evident that ASA and PP have aniso-absorptive point at 275 nm(λ_1). The second wavelength used was 267 nm (λ_2) of λ_{max} of ASA. ASA and PP showed considerable absorbance at both wavelengths, as illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Overlay spectra of Ascorbic acid and Piperine in methanol showing their iso-absorptive point at 275 nm.

Development and validation of UV spectroscopic method for simultaneous estimation of ASA and PP in methanol

ASA and PP samples were analyzed at their corresponding observed maximum absorption wavelengths, i.e., 275 nm (λ_1) and 267 nm (λ_2), respectively. The absorptivity coefficients of ASA and PP were computed at the wavelengths of 275 nm (λ_1) and 267 nm (λ_2) individually and are presented in Table 1. This was executed in triplicate. Absorptivities of ASA at λ_1 and λ_2 were determined to be 248 (ax1) and 149 (ax2), respectively. Similarly, absorptivities of PP at λ_1 and λ_2 were determined to be 281 (ay1) and 301 (ay2), respectively. Absorbance of mixture of solution was found to be 0.446 (A1) and 0.289 (A2) for ASA and PP respectively.

The concentrations of drugs Cx and Cy in the combination, determined by applying the absorbance and absorptivity coefficients to the specified equations, were found to be 0.0009 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 0.1025 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, respectively. The total absorbance of ASA and PP solution is equal to the mixture of ASA and PP solution absorbance value, here Q absorption method was mathematically proven in methanol.

Linearity and range

A calibration curve was established. The absorbance v/s concentration of the standard was graphed and the regression equations were derived as illustrated in Fig. 3 and 4 for ASA and Figures 5 and 6 for PP, respectively. Additional parameters were calculated as detailed in Table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Linearity data of ASA at 275 & 267 nm.

S. No.	ASA at λ_1 275 nm			ASA at λ_2 267 nm		
	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance * \pm SD	% RSD	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance * \pm SD	% RSD
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	5	0.055 \pm 0.001	1.818	5	0.067 \pm 0.001	1.493
2	10	0.093 \pm 0.001	1.631	10	0.111 \pm 0.001	1.368
3	15	0.134 \pm 0.001	0.746	15	0.163 \pm 0.002	1.411
4	20	0.165 \pm 0.002	1.522	20	0.211 \pm 0.001	0.723
5	25	0.203 \pm 0.002	1.236	25	0.246 \pm 0.003	1.220
6	30	0.242 \pm 0.003	1.259	30	0.293 \pm 0.005	1.938

* Average of six determinations. (SD= Standard Deviation,% RSD = Relative Standard Deviation) ($p < 0.0001$)

Table 2: Linearity data of PP at 275 & 267 nm.

S. No.	PP at λ_1 275 nm			PP at λ_2 267 nm		
	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance $*\pm\text{SD}$	% RSD	Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance $*\pm\text{SD}$	% RSD
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1	5	0.071 \pm 0.001	1.619	5	0.061 \pm 0.001	1.639
2	10	0.131 \pm 0.001	1.163	10	0.117 \pm 0.002	1.769
3	15	0.178 \pm 0.002	1.409	15	0.161 \pm 0.003	1.992
4	20	0.242 \pm 0.002	1.038	20	0.227 \pm 0.002	0.916
5	25	0.327 \pm 0.001	0.306	25	0.276 \pm 0.002	0.959
6	30	0.386 \pm 0.001	0.395	30	0.322 \pm 0.003	0.947

* Average of six determinations. (SD= Standard Deviation,% RSD = Relative Standard Deviation) (p<0.0001)

Table 3: Attributes determined for UV spectrophotometric method.

Parameters	Drug			
	ASA		PP	
Beer's Law limit ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$		5-30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$	
λ max	275 nm	267 nm	275 nm	267 nm
Correlation Coefficient (r)	0.995	0.9937	0.9956	0.998
Slope	0.0078	0.0095	0.0127	0.0108
Intercept	0.0102	0.013	0.0008	0.005
SE of Intercept	0.004494782	0.006129221	0.006778474	0.003868238
SD of Intercept	0.01100772	0.015010462	0.016600482	0.009473315
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	4.657	5.214	4.313511019	2.895
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	14.112	15.800	13.07124551	8.772

Fig. 4 Calibration curve of ASA at λ_1 = 275 nm.

Fig. 5 Calibration curve of ASA at λ_1 = 267 nm.

Fig. 6 Calibration curve of PP at $\lambda_1 = 275$ nm.

Fig. 7 Calibration curve of PP at $\lambda_1 = 267$ nm.

Precision

The %RSD of repeatability, intraday precision, and inter-day precision was determined for λ_1 and λ_2 , respectively, as presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Repeatability, intraday and interday precision of ASA and PP.

	Concentration of sample		Absorbance*±SD		% RSD	
	ASA	PP	At 275nm	At 267nm	At 275 nm	At 267nm
Interday Precision	10	10	0.093±0.001	0.115±0.001	1.075	1.679
Intraday Precision	10	10	0.089±0.001	0.118±0.001	1.034	1.121
Repeatability	10	10	0.092±0.001	0.120±0.001	1.305	1.243

Accuracy as recovery

The % recovery of ASA and PP were determined at 50%, 100% and 150% varying from 49.3% to 51%, 102.4% to 102.8% and 150% to 150.7% respectively, as presented in Table 5.

Table 5: % recovery of ASA and PP.

	Drug	Abs 1	Abs 2	Abs 3	Avg	± SD	% Recovery	Avg ± SD	% RSD
50 %	ASA	5.1	5.0	5.2	5.10	0.100	51.0	5.1±0.1	1.9608
	PP	5.0	5.0	4.9	4.97	0.058	49.3	4.933±0.057	1.1703
100%	ASA	10.4	10.1	10.2	10.24	0.150	102.4	10.243±0.15	1.4687
	PP	10.1	10.3	10.4	10.28	0.166	102.8	10.276±0.166	1.6176
150%	ASA	15.1	15.2	14.9	15.07	0.153	150.7	15.066±0.152	1.0138
	PP	14.9	15.3	14.8	15.0	0.265	150.0	15±0.264	1.7638

Forced degradation studies

ASA and PP were subjected to degradation under various circumstances, including acidic, basic, oxidative, thermal, and photolytic environments. Table 6 presents the results of the deterioration analysis. Both ASA and PP were significantly destroyed in acidic and basic

media, as well as during oxidative degradation. However, there is minimal deterioration under photolytic and thermal conditions, as presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Results of forced degradation studies of Ascorbic acid and Piperine by UV spectrophotometry.

S. No.	Forced Degradation Conditions		% Degradation Observed	
			Ascorbic acid	Piperine
1	Acid Hydrolysis	0.1M HCL (80°C, 60 min)	57.61	31.24
2	Alkali Hydrolysis	0.1M NaOH (80°C, 60 min)	89.56	55.6
3	Oxidative Degradation	30% v/v H ₂ O ₂ (Room temp., 15 min)	53.64	56.61
4	Thermal Degradation	80°C for 24 hours in hot air oven	85.17	14.84
5	Photolytic Degradation	4 hrs of exposure to direct sunlight	77.24	19.38

CONCLUSION

We have successfully developed and validated a method for the simultaneous estimation of ASA and PP in combined formulation using methanol as the solvent. The results are suitable with acceptance parameters in accordance with ICH guidelines, which are linearity, accuracy, precision, LOD and LOQ. A forced degradation research serves as an indicator of a drug's stability under stressed or extreme settings, indicating its effectiveness in detecting degradation products without interference from active ingredients which is essential for industry and academic research. Consequently, it is essential to comprehend a drug substance's purity profile and its behavior under diverse environmental conditions. Therefore, we ascertain that our newly developed UV spectrophotometric approach is a dependable indication of stability and may be employed for stability assessment.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Rizwan Ahamad: Conceived and designed the experiments; Rizwan Ahamad, Rama K.P. Performed the experiments; Nazreen Tabassum, Rizwan Ahamad: Analyzed and interpreted the data; Contributed reagents, materials, analysis tools or data; Shubham Singh, Gurpreet

Singh: Writing, review and editing the manuscript. Mohd Akhtar and Mohd Aqil: Analyzed and interpreted the data; Mohd Mujeeb: Supervised the research work..

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DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data are available on request from the corresponding author.

DECLARATIONS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Hassan HA, Ahmed HS, Hassan DF Free radicals and oxidative stress: Mechanisms and therapeutic targets. *Human Antibodies*, 2024; 32(4): 151-167.
2. Trifunsi S et al Determination of the ascorbic acid content and the antioxidant activity of different varieties of vegetables consumed in Romania, from farmers and supermarkets. *Sustainability*, 2022; 14(21): 13749.
3. Afkhami-Ardekani M, Shojaoddiny-Ardekani A. Effect of vitamin C on blood glucose, serum lipids & serum insulin in type 2 diabetes patients. *Indian Journal of medical research*, 2007; 126(5): 471-474.
4. El-Borm H, Badawy GM, El-Nabi SH, El-Sherif W, Atallah M. Efficacy of curcumin on sunset yellow and tartrazine induced hepatotoxicity and nephrotoxicity in the chick embryo *Gallus domesticus*. *Ejpmr*, 2019; 6: 48-64.
5. AbouAitah K et al. Effective targeting of colon cancer cells with piperine natural anticancer prodrug using functionalized clusters of hydroxyapatite nanoparticles. *Pharmaceutics*, 2020; 12(1): 70.
6. Kurangi B, Jalalpure S. A validated stability-indicating RP-HPLC method for piperine estimation in black pepper, marketed formulation and nanoparticles. *Indian J Pharm Educ Res.*, 2020; 54(3s): s677-86.

7. Jain PS, Chaudhari AJ, Patel SA, Patel ZN, Patel DT. Development and validation of the UV-spectrophotometric method for determination of terbinafine hydrochloride in bulk and in formulation. *Pharmaceutical methods*, 2011; 2(3): 198-202.
8. Lotfy HM, Saleh SS, Hassan NY, Salem H. A comparative study of novel spectrophotometric methods based on isosbestic points; application on a pharmaceutical ternary mixture. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 2014; 126: 112-121.
9. Tayde A. Forced Degradation Studies: Analytical Methodologies, Applications, and Regulatory Insights—A Systematic Review. *Journal of Drug Delivery and Biotherapeutics*, 2024; 1(02): 13-23.
10. Singh DK, Singh S, Bajaj S. Regulatory guidelines on stability testing and trending of requirements. In *Methods for Stability Testing of Pharmaceuticals*, 1-30. New York, NY: Springer New York, 2018.
11. Guideline, IHT Validation of analytical procedures: text and methodology. *Q2 (R1)*, 2005; 1(20): 05.
12. Majithia RH, Khodadiya A, Patel VB Spectrophotometric method development and validation for simultaneous estimation of Anagliptin and Metformin HCl BY Q-Absorption ratio method in synthetic mixture. *Heliyon*, 2020; 6(5).
13. Sultana N at al. Development And Validation of UV-Spectroscopy Based Stability Indicating Method For Simultaneous Estimation of Risedronate Sodium And Ursolic Acid. *World J Pharm Res.*, 2022; 11: 1293-306.
14. Ali A et al. Development and validation of UV-spectroscopy based stability indicating method for simultaneous determination of fluoxetine hydrochloride and embelin, 2022.